

KIMMDY

bwRSE4HPC Project Report

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Project Partners:	Eric Hartmann ¹² , Jannik Buhr ¹² , Frauke Gräter ¹²
Scientific field:	Physics
Subfield:	Molecular Dynamics
Duration:	6 weeks
Type of Work	HPC porting
License:	GPL
Link:	https://github.com/graeter-group/kimmdy
Programming Language:	Python
Technologies:	Tensorflow, PyTorch, CUDA
Target Cluster:	Helix

1 Overview of the planned project

KIMMDY is a kinematic Monte Carlo code that has been developed for molecular dynamics (MD). KIMMDY acts as an interface for different reactions and topologies to act on molecules. These processes can be provided through the plug-in interface of KIMMDY, allowing users to define their own plug-ins and making the code extensible.

The molecular dynamics part of KIMMDY utilizes GROMACS, a highly parallelized molecular dynamics code for simulating the Newtonian dynamics of many particles. Primarily designed for biological and organic molecules, GROMACS can simulate the structure and motion of large and relatively complex molecules, such as proteins and lipids. The software additionally makes use of GPU acceleration with CUDA to produce results efficiently.

The project partners have requested help with three issues for bwRSE4HPC to help address ahead of KIMMDY's publication:

1. KIMMDY and relevant plugins require different dependencies from each other, making the installation of KIMMDY complex. The goal here, with the help of bwRSE4HPC, is to consolidate and update a singular set of dependencies for KIMMDY and all its packages.
2. The plugins for the HAT reaction and GRAPPA make use of machine learning models to make predictions for reactions and topologies, respectively. When run with KIMMDY, two GPUs are currently required due to the plugins and GROMACS needing GPUs. However, since these steps occur interdependently of each other, only one GPU is needed at a time. A way to free the GPU memory between processes needs to be implemented.
3. Lastly, KIMMDY currently only contains unit tests for testing functionality. A set of integration tests are required for the code's publication to ensure its many components work together.

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2 Addressing the request

2.1 Dependencies

The KIMMDY ecosystem consists of the main KIMMDY package and currently five plugins. To simplify the dependency management, the project was restructured. The main repository now links the officially supported plugins as sub-repositories. Further, the recommended development setup now uses `uv`, and the plugins are registered in a `uv-workspace`. This workspace allows compiling the dependencies of all packages into one lock file, ensuring compatibility.

Due to the many dependencies, installation using `pip` was slow, the new recommended installation method using `uv` is significantly faster. `pip` is still supported however.

Lastly, the switch to `uv` allows installation of KIMMDY and all plugins, including the machine learning frameworks used, and the python runtime with a single command. This should make setup on HPC infrastructure trivial.

The documentation was updated accordingly.

Support for the newest Gromacs version 2025 was added, further simplifying the setup, as now Gromacs no longer needs to be patched with `plumed` during compilation.

The KIMMDY-HAT reaction plugin was published on PyPi for easy installation.

2.2 Freeing the GPU

The project partners were experiencing an issue with GPU memory usage, in which Tensorflow was not releasing the GPU memory after the models were loaded and used. When KIMMDY would start an MD simulation in another step, gromacs was unable to use the GPU as a result. Tensorflow itself does not provide a method to release GPU memory, only when the parent process ends is it freed. Therefore, all code using Tensorflow was encapsulated into a separate process, which can be terminated after the HAT predictions are done for a simulation. The models now need to be loaded for every HAT reaction step in KIMMDY, rather than just at the start of the program. Although this increases the overhead each time the HAT reaction is performed, it is negligible compared to the subsequent equilibrium step with GROMACS (~22 s vs 12 hours).

The following steps were implemented:

1. `make_predictions` was encapsulated in a separate process to ensure the reserved memory gets freed after use by tensorflow.
2. Separated all use of tensorflow into `make_predictions`
3. Model architecture was modified to use the GPU more efficiently. (Factor ~ 8 speed up during HAT prediction)

After implementation, the RSEs tested the HAT reaction in KIMMDY with the standard alanine example provided and monitored the usage on both one and two GPUs. In both cases, the memory was freed after each step of the simulation, removing the need for two GPUs to be required to run KIMMDY.

As an additional layer of security, a unit test called `test_gpu_memory_release` was implemented into the plug-in's testing framework. By default, this test is skipped by `pytest` unless the flag `--gpu` is used.

2.3 Integration tests

The project partners required the implementation of integration tests for each plug-in that required one. The RSEs generated the integration tests as detailed in table 1, following a similar framework for the integration tests that already exist within KIMMDY:

Reaction plugin name	Reaction	Integration test type	Molecule used
kimmdy-hat	Hydrogen atom transfer	full sim. & restart	Alanine
kimmdy-hydrolysis	Hydrolysis	full sim. & restart	Glycine
kimmdy-dimerization	Dimerization	full sim. & restart	DNA

Table 1: List of added integration tests to the KIMMDY plugins.

The integration tests were tested on both Helix and the CI pipeline present with GitHub Actions and all currently pass. The notable exception is the integration tests of kimmdy-hydrolysis which were only ran on Helix. This is due to the integration tests taking too long for the CI pipeline.

In addition to the development of the integration tests, testing frameworks for kimmdy-hydrolysis and kimmdy-dimerization were established for their respective CI pipelines, making use of tox.

By adding various tests, coverage of KIMMDY was increased by 4% to 77%.